

A study on Online Consumer Buying Behavior during Festive Seasons in India

V T Shailashri*, Dr.P.S.Aithal**, Dr. Surekha Shenoy**

*Research scholar Srinivas University

**Professor, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore 575001, India

shailashrivt@gmail.com

Abstract

21st century is an era of digitization, where everything is available online from groceries to gadgets. Consumers today are cognizing the benefits of digitization and asking for more personalized dominion. While consumers in large metros are opting for online retail and e-commerce for most of their purchases, the trend is slowly penetrating in non-metro cities as well.

Rising incomes in the hands of a young population, a growing economy, expansion in the availability of products and services and easy availability of credit all has given rise to new consumer segments and a rising acceptability of debt, whether it is mobile phones, credit cards, apparel or organized retail, people clearly seem to be spending more, particularly on discretionary items. The credit facility from business houses has been increasing at a rapid rate. This shows the terrific cut-throat competition in the ever changing market.

Festival Sales are a latest fad in India contributing tremendously to the growth of the online sales. All marketing retailers use the festival time to promote their products – either new or stock clearance products at heavy discounts or other offers (freebies, cash backs, buy 1 get 1 etc), The major shopping festival in India comes around the period of the period of October-November when Diwali is celebrated and most of the online e commerce sites provide big ticket offers during this period having created unique names for such shopping events – for example – Big billion days by Flipkart, Great Indian Shopping Festival by Amazon to name some. This study is an attempt to understand consumer buying behavior in India during the festive season.

Keywords: Consumer buying behavior, online marketing, festive season, digitization

1. INTRODUCTION

Festival Sales are a latest fad in India contributing tremendously to the growth of the online sales. All marketing retailers use the festival time to promote their products – either new or stock clearance products at heavy discounts or other offers (freebies, cash backs, buy 1 get 1 etc),[1] The major shopping festival in India comes around the period of the period of October- November when Diwali is celebrated and most of the online e commerce sites provide big ticket offers during this period having created unique names for such shopping events – for example – Big billion days by Flipkart, Great Indian Shopping Festival by Amazon to name some.[2]

2. CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR

Consumer behaviour deals with the study of buying behaviour of consumers. Consumer behaviour helps us understand why and why not an individual purchases goods and services from the market. The study of consumer behaviour explains as to:[3]

- Why and why not a consumer buys a product?
- When a consumer buys a product?
- How a consumer buys a product?

Consumer Behaviour is a branch which deals with the various stages a consumer goes through before purchasing products or services for his end use.

Why do you think an individual buys a product?

- Need
- Social Status
- Gifting Purpose

Why do you think an individual does not buy a product?

- No requirement
- Income/Budget/Financial constraints
- Taste

When do you think consumers purchase products?

- Festive season
- Birthday
- Anniversary
- Marriage or other special occasions

There are in fact several factors which influence buying decision of a consumer ranging from psychological, social, and economic and so on.[4]

The four type of consumer buying behavior are:

- Routine Response/Programmed Behavior □ buying low involvement frequently purchased low cost items; need very little search and decision effort; purchased almost automatically. Examples include soft drinks, snack foods, milk etc.[5][6]
- Limited Decision Making □ buying product occasionally. When you need to obtain information about unfamiliar brand in a familiar product category, perhaps. Requires a moderate amount of time for information gathering. Examples include Clothes--know product class but not the brand.]7][8]
- Extensive Decision Making □ Complex high involvement, unfamiliar, expensive and/or infrequently bought products. High degree of economic/performance/psychological risk. Examples include cars, homes, computers, education. Spend a lot of time seeking information and deciding. Information from the companies MM; friends and relatives, store personnel etc. Go through all six stages of the buying process.
- Impulse buying □ no conscious planning.[9]

3. Objectives

The study is being carried out to understand the following key parameters apart from other parameters as part of the survey:

1. Various Factors that contribute highly towards festival spends which determine the consumer buying behaviour.
2. Percentage of people who shop online

4. METHODOLOGY

Primary Data collection with a small sample of 30 respondents. An Online Google form questionnaire has been devised for the same that enlists questions evoking different responses from the consumers. The responses were coded and entered in SPSS to generate different levels of output analysis in the form of tables and charts.

Understanding the respondents - Frequency Distribution

Location					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Airoli	1	3.3	3.3	3.3
	Bangalore	8	26.7	26.7	30.0
	Chennai	1	3.3	3.3	33.3
	Goa	2	6.7	6.7	40.0
	Kasargod	1	3.3	3.3	43.3
	Kuwait	1	3.3	3.3	46.7
	Mangalore	12	40.0	40.0	86.7
	Manipal	1	3.3	3.3	90.0
	Mumbai	2	6.7	6.7	96.7
	Udupi	1	3.3	3.3	100.0
	Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	14	46.7	46.7	46.7
	Female	16	53.3	53.3	100.0
	Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below 20 years	3	10.0	10.0	10.0
	20 - 30 years	16	53.3	53.3	63.3
	30 - 40 years	11	36.7	36.7	100.0
	Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation

- From the above tables, we can understand that most of the respondents are from Mangalore and Bangalore and in general from the South part of India.
- The percentage of Males and Females respondents are almost the same.
- Age wise, most of the respondents are above 20 years up to 40 years with **53.3%** from the 20 to 30 years age bracket.

Graphical Interpretation

Interpretation

- The above pie chart reveals that nearly 73.3% of the respondents shop during a festival sales (note: the others are also online shoppers but need not shop during a festival sale)

Interpretation

- The above pie chart reveals that **56.673%** of the respondents wait for a festival sale before they decide on purchasing a product and **46.33%** do not wait for a festival sale, they just purchase as when they need the product. This reveals the eagerness of the consumer and the popularity of festival sales.

Simple Frequency Distribution

Different Websites Comparison					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	7	23.3	23.3	23.3
	Yes	23	76.7	76.7	100.0
	Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation

- A simple frequency on the variable “Different Websites Comparison” which tries to find out how many respondents refer different websites before they decide on shopping from a particular website reveals that **76.7%** respondents do so.

56.67% of the respondents wait for a festival sale before they decide on purchasing a product and **46.33%** do not wait for a festival sale, they just purchase as when they need the product.

76.7% respondents prefer to review products on other websites before deciding to do a purchase.

SUGGESTIONS & CONCLUSION

A sample study of 30 respondents geographically scattered in different cities mostly in South India and with 53% respondents in the 20 to 30 Years age bracket, a detailed SPSS analysis revealed that Festival sales is indeed very beneficial for the marketers. Marketers will need to take holistic approach in preparing marketing campaigns for their products to be promoted during a festival sale on the different ecommerce sites. Flipkart and Amazon are their best bets in deriving profits. No separate marketing strategy is required to target men and women separately as the proportions of the gender shopping during festival sale are the same? The strategy of tying up with Banks and offering discounts on the cards works quite well as seen from the analysis. The promotion efforts can be maintained be distributed evenly over all the days of a festival as it does not make any difference if the efforts are concentrated on the first day or the last day since from our analysis we see that the day and expenditure are not related. Festival sales campaigns and products can be targeted more on Women as they are very impulsive in their buying behaviour and do not wait for a festival sale. There is still scope in this study to be further revised in terms of the questionnaire and to increase the sample count and come up with a more detailed study in the future

- [1] Ahuja, R.D.B. and K.M. Stinson (1993). „Female-Headed Single Parent Families! An Exploratory Study of Children’s Influence in Family Decision Making.“ *Advances in Consumer Research*. 20. 469-474.
- [2] Alda Heunis (2003). „Responsible Marketing to Kids“ *Public Relations News*. (August). from http://www.biz_community.com
- [3] Atkin, C. (1978) „Observation of Parent-Child Interaction in Supermarket Decision-Making.“ *Journal of Marketing*. 42. (October). 41-45.
- [4] Bahn, K.D. (1986). „How and When Do Brand Perceptions and Preferences First Form? A Cognitive Developmental Investigation.“ *Journal of Consumer Research*. 13. (December). 382-393.
- [5] Bakshi Vikram. „Kids are No Longer Passive Members of the Family.“ *Kid Pulse*. <http://www.agencyfaqs.org/> Bansal, R. (2004).
- [6] Aliens.“ *Business world*. (June). <http://www.businessworldindia.com/June2804/coverstory05.asp>.
- [7] Barletta Martha (2003). „Build Sales and Boost Share by Tapping into Women’s Buying Power.“ *Sales and Marketing Excellence*. (February). www.martha.barletta@trendsight.com.
- [8] M.L. Hoffman and L.W. Hoffman (Eds.), New York : Russel sage. 169-204. [cited in Carlson and Grossbart (1988)].
- [9] Belch, G., M.A. Belch, and G. Ceresino (1985). *Parental and Teenage Influences in*

Family Decision-Making.” Journal of Business Research. 13. (April). 163-176.